

The vicissitudes of monetary policy rates and Macro-economic Variables in the West African Monetary Zone

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Abstract

This study offers an empirical investigation into some selected macroeconomic drivers of the monetary policy rate in member countries of the West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ), considering both internal and external variables. We employed ARDL to investigate monetary policy and some macroeconomic variables in both the long-run and short-run relationship. The results suggest that the drivers of the policy rate in this zone, in the long run, include among others, global oil price, exchange rate, inflation rate, and gross domestic product, while in the short run, federal fund rate, trade openness, exchange rate, inflation rate, and gross domestic product are core determinants of the policy rate. Therefore, in order to ensure long-run stability in the policy rate among the members' states, these drivers should be given closer consideration, so that trajectory for effective structure can be designed and fused into the economic structure and policy frameworks accordingly.

Keywords: Monetary policy rate, Macroeconomic variables, WAMZ, ARDL

1. Introduction

The monetary authorities have identified monetary policy as one of the major instruments for regulating the economy to the long-run equilibrium level owing to its suitability and efficiency [18]. The aptitude of the monetary policy to achieve the targeted macroeconomic objectives is a function of many factors which include, among others, the potency of the Central bank, the analytical capability of the monetary authority as well as the stage of development of such country's financial system. It is imperative to note that the impact of the monetary policy rate for optimum resource allocation for growth, stability, and economic development cannot be undermined [44]. Thus, in developing economies, like WAMZ, the strategy and implementation of policy rates are very crucial with regard to the allocation of resources, savings, control of inflation as well as growth enhancement.

The main issue is how to guarantee a realistic policy rate in developing economies that are dominated by imperfect and oligopolistic market structures [41]. Indeed, the determination of the policy rate through market forces is not feasible, thus the intervention of monetary authorities in some instances cannot be denied. Hence, it is of paramount importance to identify the macroeconomic effects of policy rates, specifically in developing economies like the West African Monetary zone. The knowledge about the determination of the policy rate is further justified by the fact that the policy rate is not only for the purpose of economic growth and stability but also a vital instrument for the transmission of monetary policy shocks. For instance, the policy rate is the major instrument for steering monetary policy. Also, the responsiveness of investment and aggregate demand is conditional to policy rate adjustments.

There are other conflicting issues on the relationship between the monetary policy rates and macroeconomic variables, without consensus. For example, some views conceived that the shock of the oil price of the 70s accounted for the macroeconomic performance of that period. Conversely, another view believes that it was the reaction of monetary policy to the oil price shock that really stimulated macroeconomic instability, at that time [40]. The empirical results of [20] indicate that the relationship between the policy rate and oil price is inverse, but the relationship could not be held after the 80s. on the other hand, [21] find a relatively non-significant relation

between oil price and policy rate. Also, there is no consensus on the relationship between the policy rate and the output. The findings of [43] indicate that policy rate increase does not significantly affect economic growth. Conversely, [33], [23], among others, suggested that policy rate enhances growth. These conflicting issues form part of the contributions of this study.

This study, therefore, offers empirical evidence on internal and external driving factors of the policy rate, both in the short and long runs for economic stabilization, in WAMZ. The practical implication of considering both internal and external factors in modeling the driving factors of policy rates in the monetary zone assists in the generation of possible results for a more reliable economic analysis and forecast.

Literature review

Over time, the role of monetary policy particularly, policy rate in resource allocation, economic growth and stability, capital accumulation and development cannot be undermined (see [44] [27], [4]). The classical theorists, using the loanable fund as a basis for the interest rate determination stressed the interactions between the demand and supply of savings and investments in an economy. This is similar to the Keynesian framework of the theory of liquidity preference, which also centers on the interface between the demand for money and the money supply.

The arguments of the policy rate proponents are that monetary policy stimulates an increase in nominal interest rate; considering its long-run effects, the investors encourage changes in the anticipated risk returns on their assets [16]. In q-theory of investment through the asset price transmission channel views the investors' expectation on the nexus in risk-return. Policy changes of increase in interest rates entice investors on the debt instruments. Monetary tightening leads to a decrease in q , which results in a decline in output and employment.

In an open economy, monetary tightening through an increase in policy rates necessitates devaluation of the local currency which equates to risk-adjusted returns on the instruments of debt, which is necessary for the uncovered interest rate parity. Therefore, the prices slowly adjust to a rise in the value of the local currency, a rise in the cost of domestic goods, and subsequently a fall in output, employment, and net exports [4]. This is in line with [32] that the devaluation of currency is inflationary, rise in import and general prices, which leads to a rise in demand for money with consequential side effects on the policy rate of the economy. In Fisher's theoretical framework,

while analyzing the nexus between the policy rate and inflation he argued that in the long run, as a result of the variations in the money supply, the policy rate eventually adjusts to fluctuations in inflation expectations. Hence, if Fisher's proposition holds, it would affect the monetary policy of the developing economies.

The relationship between the policy rate and inflation in Ghana was investigated by [1] using a data set between 1960 and 2009. The results show a positive relationship, which was due to the use of short-term interest rates by the Central Bank as the prime policy anchor for its inflation-targeting policy. [12] examined the long-run relationship between the inflation rate and interest rate for 8 Euro countries and the US, using the cointegration method. The results suggest that Euro currency and inflation have a causal relationship of one-on-one. The study stated that the incorporation of market participants would integrate a probable percentage of the inflation rate into the interest rate. The analysis of [5] on the connection between policy rates and inflation suggests a negative relationship as hypothesized by [19]. However, the relationship was reported to be weak [28], [2].

The findings of [43] in respect of the policy rate nexus GDP, support that interest rate is one of the factors driving the economic growth of an economy. Thus, a hike in interest rate shows a dwindling GDP. The findings further indicate that policy rate increase does not significantly affect economic growth. This is contrary to the findings of [33], that found that a hike in interest rate leads to an increase in real GDP, which indicates that policy rate impacts economic growth. This is similar to [23] who used a data set from 2000 to 2016 in South Africa and employed a quantitative approach, including ARDL, to analyze the existing relationship among foreign direct investment (FDI), GDP and repo rate in south Africa. The author found a negative long-run relationship between the repo rate and GDP, but a positive and significant impact in the short run was the relationship between the FDI and the repo rate in the short run

The investigation of [26] was on the dynamic relationship between the US policy rates FFR and treasury bill (3 months) rate. The authors employed daily data ranging from 1974 to 199 and found a solid relationship between the variables which were steady in all the monetary policy regimes. Monetary transmission channels were analysed by [16] between the FFR and the prime interest rate, using VECM. The findings suggest the impact of FFR on prime interest rate was solid in the long run. That is FFR constitutes the driver towards the long-run equilibrium. Similarly, [6]

examined the relationship between long term interest rates and FFR. The study extends the interest rates to include yield on corporate bond and Treasury bond of 30-year term. The results depict a cointegrated relationship between the long-term interest rates and the FFR while the impact of the FFR on the long-term interest rates is not significant in the short run. The FFR nexus domestic interest rates were investigated by [36], using Johansen cointegrated model and VEC. The author's finding is that the domestic interest rate (fixed mortgage interest rate) cointegrates with the FFR. In addition, the causality passes through the latter to the former.

In respect of the relationship between the monetary policy rate and the global oil price, [29] investigated this in China economy, using diverse econometric models including, Time Varying Parameter SVAR (TVP SVAR) and VAR(SVAR) with short run recognizing restrictions. The analysis depicts mixed results at different times. The policy rate depicts a negative response to the oil price variation between 1992:4–2001:10, and thereafter shows that the response was positive within the period 2001:11–2014:5. The negative response to the interest rate implies a boosting economy, while the positive response is evidence of inflation stabilization of the monetary authority in China, even though the main objective is on stabilization of the value of the domestic currency for enhancing economic growth. The investigation of [42] into the effect of the oil price volatility on macroeconomic variables in Nigeria, using EGARCH and Lag-augmented VAR (LA_VAR) models. The authors evidently found the existence of a unidirectional relationship from oil price to interest rate and exchange rate. Thus, similar to the findings of [9], global oil price, working through the exchange rate, is a substantial determinant to the policy rate in the long run.

[14] analyzed the influence of trade openness and trade policy on the effectiveness of the monetary policy in Ghana. The study adopted a cointegration approach and employed a quarterly data set from 2002 to 2016 for its investigation. The empirical findings suggest that increased trade openness reduces the efficacy of the monetary policy. [26] investigated the influence of openness on monetary policy as it affects output in 8 countries (Australia, Canada, Germany, Italy, Japan, South Africa, the U.K., and the U.S.A.). The study employed quarterly data from 1960 to 1994. The results conform to the theoretical expectation that openness hypothetically diminishes the capacity of the variations in the money supply to impact the economic activity of a country. That is, with a given change in monetary policy, output decreases relative to trade openness.

In the empirical study of [18] the findings indicated that a negative relationship exists between the policy rates and exchange rates. This is contrary to Berument and Gumay (2003) that the relationship is direct. That is, increasing the policy rates leads to an increase in the exchange rates, which implies a depreciation of the local currency. [11] examined a cross-sectional relationship between short-term interest rates and exchange rates in 80 countries. The empirical results suggest a non-monotonic relationship; a little rise in the interest rate leads to currency appreciation, but a higher increase depreciates the currency. Money demand is increased with higher interest rates, which further increases the fiscal deficit and weakens output and consequently leads to currency depreciation. [8] analyzed 14 emerging countries and some economies in the Euro area for the period 2001–2014. The result revealed that monetary policy as a macroprudential tool fails to be effective when interest rates are changed subject to capital flow. [3] on Romania's economy, adopted wavelet theory to analyze the relationship between interest rate and exchange rate with daily data for the period 1999 – 2004. The authors find that the two variables had co-movements through policy changes and challenging periods. There is a negative relationship during the short term and positive relationships at the long term. [9], [28] studies the monetary policy mechanism effect in Turkey between the period 1968 and 2000. The paper discoursed that the innovation in the monetary policy within this period of study was the dispersal between the local currency depreciation rate and the interest rate of the Central Bank. A restricted monetary policy leads to a general price reduction and income and currency appreciation

Furthermore, [28] focused on developed economies by using VAR models to examine the monetary policy effects on the exchange rate. The results show that contractionary monetary policy results in a significant appreciation of the exchange rate. [30] on Serbia's economy, reports that the exchange rate seems to respond more significantly than policy rates to monetary policy interference. This is adduced to the fact that it exerts more impact on inflation than on other real economic variables. It is prominent among emerging economies to amass foreign currency reserves to confront the challenges of inflation, being inflation-targeting and exchange rate depreciation economies, which eventually affects the long-term interest rates. [24] adopted a Keynesian model to analyze the interest rate and exchange rate nexus in a “soft peg” nominal exchange rate regime. The model suggests multiple equilibria with the assumption of an imperfect financial market under the unrestricted monetary policy. In developing countries, empirical studies have suggested probable asymmetric effects of the exchange rate on the interest rate. Recently,

[13] employed the ARDL model to explore the relationship between interest rates and exchange rates as a response to the action of the monetary authority in Mexico's economy. The results suggest an asymmetrical relationship between policy rate and exchange rate nexus. The exchange rate significantly affects the interest rates in the long run. Conversely, the interest rate wields no significant influence on the exchange rate.

2. METHODOLOGY

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model has been considered appropriate for this study. The use of this approach is considered fit for the study based on its accrued advantages among which include its flexibility, particularly its applicability regardless of whether the variables are integrated of the same order. ARDL helps to assess the determinants of the fluctuations of the monetary policy rates, both in the short and long run. The model also has the capacity of accommodating enough lag numbers of a set of data from general to the specific model framework. [35], [31]. Other merits of ARDL that cannot be undermined include its applicability for investigating both long-run and short-run dynamics and its ability to accommodate varied lags of the variable [31]; it is suitable for large and small samples sizes [39]. It is also a model that accounts for cross-sectional dependence in a panel data analysis [15].

Model Specification

This study focuses on the relationship between the policy rate and some designated macro-economic variables including gross domestic product, trade openness, inflation rate, and exchange rate as well as external variables of trade openness and federal funds rate constituting the exogenous variables.

The Panel ARDL model could generally be stated in the form

$$Y_{i,t} = \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_{i,j} Y_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^n \delta'_{i,j} X_{i,t-j} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where Y denotes the dependent variable, X represents the vector of the explanatory variables.

In the case of this study Y represents the monetary policy rate, while X encompasses GDP, INF, TOP, EXCH, FFR, and GPR).

By parametrizing we have:

$$\Delta Y_{i,t} = \phi_i \left(Y_{i,t-1} - \beta'_i X_{i,t} \right) + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \alpha^*_{i,j} \Delta Y_{i,t} \alpha_{i,t-j} Y_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \delta^*_{i,j} \Delta X_{i,t-j} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \quad (2)$$

Where β_i indicates the vector of interest for the measurement of the long-run influence of the explanatory variables. ϕ_i is an error correction mechanism. Other parameters are the short-run coefficients. ε_{it} represents the disturbances with iid (i.e Zero mean and constant variance within units).

Equation (1) of the model permits parameters to change between units, which can be estimated with a mean group estimator for the estimation of each country and group mean. Nevertheless, for homogenous long-run coefficients across the group., the model permits the use of a pooled mean group. This allows the parameters to fluctuate between countries in the short run, while the parameters are required to be homogenous in the long run [36], [37], [17].

3. Data and definition of Variables

Data: This study employs a quarterly data, which spans over the period 1980(Q1) to 2020(Q4). This is based on the belief that it is a period long enough to capture the growth trends, inflationary trends, and the movements in the business cycles. The intention here is to cover the global financial crisis periods in the monetary policy, between 1980 to the recent one of 2014, during which the sub-region of WAMZ economies were not exempted. Subject to availability of data, this study covers four countries in WAMZ countries (The Gambia, Ghana, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone).

Variables: The Monetary policy rate is the dependent variable. The study used the gross domestic product rate (GDP): It is used in the study as the proxy for economic growth. Exchange rate (EXR)- It is the value of the national currency per USD. An increase in the exchange rate implies a depreciation of the country's currency. ECOWAS being an open economy necessitates the introduction of the variable into the model. Trade openness (TOP) - This is exports plus imports as per cent of GDP and Inflation Rate (INF)- This is proxy with the Period average consumer price index (2010 = 100). This is the general increase in the price level. The external variables include

the global oil price and the Federal funds rate. Global Oil price (GPR) and Federal funds rate (FFR) are incorporated as exogenous variables of the domestic economy. The inclusion of these exogenous variables centres on the dominant roles played by the US on global influence with the attendant spillover effects that cannot be undermined. This is because the economic development of the US certainly has a substantial impact on the global economy, West Africa inclusive, as a result of its international relations, coupled with its size, the magnitude of foreign direct investments and its organized financial markets [38].

Sources: The gross domestic product is obtained from WDI, while the exchange rate, policy rate and inflation rate were obtained from IMF, and IFS statistical data. The trade openness data is extracted from AfDB socio-economic database. The data on global oil prices and federal funds rate were collected from the Federal Reserve Bank of St Louis (Federal Reserve economic data). All the data set covers the period 1980 to 2020.

4. Results of the estimates

Basically, the preliminary investigation commenced, with the presentation of descriptive statistics to give the summary of the data employed and the conduction of a panel unit root test to determine the fitness of the variables employed for the panel model.

We also test for the existence of unit root (stationarity) using the IPS and ADF tests. The use of the two approaches is for the purpose of comparison and validating results [22]. Before the panel model estimation, this study tested for heterogeneity and homogeneity (cross-country) using the standard unit root test. The test is grounded on the usual coefficient pair-wise correlation of the residual of OLS which is derived from ADF regressions. The Null hypothesis suggests cross-sectional neutrality and asymptotical distribution being a two-tailed normal distribution. Results show the variables employed are non-stationary and are integrated of order one i.e. $I(1)$. at 5% significant levels. None of the variables are integrated into $I(2)$, which complies with [37] on ARDL modeling.

5. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table 1 shows the summary of the result of the descriptive statistics for the 608 observations for WAMZ. It indicates the statistics relating to the mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, and skewness of the distribution in WAMZ.

The mean values of the variables of MPR, GPR, FFR, TOP, INF and EXCH are nearer to their respective minimum values than the maximum. This implies that the data set for WAMZ are concentrated at the lower band of the distribution. The value of the probability affirms that the data distribution is free of heteroscedasticity of the model, which is at a significance level of less than 1%. This implies that both the data and the residuals used for the modelling WAMZ are normally distributed. The data set skewed to the right as they all have positive values. Nonetheless, the normality tests of the Jarque-Bera, and Kurtosis show normality.

Table 1: Summary of statistics WAMZ

	MPR	GPR	FFR	GDP	TOP	INF	EXCH
Mean	17.92576	3.51173	4.799211	1.10E+10	0.015075	159.1443	186.4020
Maximum	63.78776	4.807921	19.10000	1.40E+11	0.064261	1164.991	2679.101
Minimum	0.546875	2.406044	0.070000	68296103	5.64E-05	0.032330	0.000503
Std Dev.	10.47561	0.658957	4.101932	2.70E+10	0.012309	202.0396	468.4798
Skewness	1.380301	0.444116	1.005421	3.279231	1.534223	2.139098	3.042942
Kurtosis	6.954056	2.076216	4.198264	12.85820	5.159081	8.406940	11.98577
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Observations	608	608	608	608	608	608	608

Source: Author's computation from data obtained from WDIanf AfDB (2023).

5.2 Panel unit root tests results

Another important pre-condition required for the estimation of the data panel analysis is the conduct of the unit root test for the variables employed. The Im Pesaran & Shin (IPS) and ADF Fisher panel unit root test presented in Table 2 showed the nature of stationarity of variables used in the study. As reported in Table 2, the selected variables reflect integrating order one. Specifically result showed that MPR, FFR, GPR, EXC, INF, and GDP are stationary after the first difference, meaning they are integrated of order one I(1), which conforms to one of the conventional

requirements of ARDL estimation. By implication, the unit root test reflects that the variables retained innovative shock passed on them for a short period.

Table 2: Panel Unit Root Test (WAMZ)

Variables	<i>Im, Pesaran and Shin IPS</i>		<i>ADF Fisher</i>	
	IPS Stat	Order of Integration	ADF Stat	Order of Integration
MPR	-8.22272*	I(1)	84.1223*	I(1)
FFR	-6.74626*	I(1)	63.3717*	I(1)
GPR	-12.4043*	I(1)	150.434*	I(1)
TOP	-16.8617*	I(1)	221.765*	I(1)
EXC	-2.24664*	I(1)	28.7756*	I(1)
INF	-3.10159*	I(1)	26.4233	I(1)
GDP	-6.78150	I(1)	64.8565	I(1)

Source: Author's computation from data obtained from WDIanf AfDB (2021).

5.1 Panel Cointegration Test

Table 3 shows the summary of panel co-integration tests of Kao, Pedroni and Fisher conducted in this study. Results reported for both monetary union and monetary zone showed validation for rejection of null hypothesis of 'no co-integration' between policy rate and determinant variables included into the model of the study. This is therefore evidence in the panel data sets suggesting long run relationship amongst the variables. Specifically reported statistics for monetary union stood at -6.370641 ($p < 0.05$) for Kao adf stat, 2.157605 ($p < 0.05$), and -2.581344 ($p < 0.05$) for Pedroni v-stat and ADF-stat, while Fisher result stood at 53.60 ($p < 0.05$) and 39.37 ($p < 0.05$) for trace and max eigen stats respectively. For monetary zone, result stood at -5.416045 ($p < 0.05$) for Kao adf stat, -0.017833 ($p > 0.05$) and -3.898753 ($p < 0.05$) for Pedroni v-stat and ADF-stat, while Fisher result stood at 91.55 ($p < 0.05$) and 58.39 ($p < 0.05$) for trace and max eigen stats respective.

Table 3: Panel Co-integration Test

MONETARY ZONE				
	Tests	Stats	Stat Values	Prob
1	KAO TEST	(ADF-stat)	-5.416045*	0.0000
2	PEDRONI TEST	(v-stat)	-0.017833	0.5071
		(ADF-stat)	-3.898753*	0.0000
3	FISHER TEST	(trace stat)	91.55*	0.0000
		(Max-eigen stat)	58.39*	0.0000

Note: * connote significance at 5% level of significant; (Fisher test report test with respect to rejection of 'none' cointegrating equation, details for other no of cointegrating equation is contained in the appendix)

Source: Author's computation from data obtained from WDIanf AfDB (2021).

In brief, there is strong evidence in support of co-integration between interest rate and determinant variables identified in the study. Thus, investigation into the long run equilibrium interrelationship between interest and the determinant variables is methodologically valid using panel ARDL estimation that can trace both long run and short run positions. Hence, this study engaged panel ARDL estimation in this respect.

5.2 Panel ARDL Estimation

Following the order of integration of the set of variables included in the study as established by the unit root test reported above. Panel ARDL model was estimated for the zone (Table 4) reflecting both the long-run and short-run effect of the selected variables in this study on the monetary policy rate. The global oil price and the Federal fund rates are the two exogenous variables introduced in this estimate which the ECOWAS member countries do not have control over, while other variables including trade openness, exchange rate, inflation, and growth can be controlled by these countries.

Table 4: PMG Estimation Result (WAMZ)

Variables	<i>Long Run estimates</i>	
	Coefficient	Probability
FFR	-0.027838	0.1981
GPR	1.073791*	0.0003
TOP	-0.075586	0.2226
EXC	-0.275919*	0.0000
INF	0.304021*	0.0000
GDP	-0.391941*	0.0000
<i>Short Run Estimates</i>		
Variables	Coefficient	Probability
COINTEQ01	-0.098084*	0.0092
D(INTR(-1))	0.413601*	0.0000
D(INTR(-2))	0.100768*	0.0010
D(FFR)	-0.008631	0.1397
D(GPR)	-0.027218	0.3552
D(TOP)	0.046061	0.3412
D(EXC)	-0.717767	0.1098
D(INF)	1.876413	0.2313
D(GDP)	-0.021720	0.8144
C	0.796645	0.0104

Source: Author's computation from data obtained from WDIanf AfDB (2021)

The results show that in the long run global oil price (GPR), exchange rate (EXC), inflation rate (INF) and gross domestic product (GDP) exert significant influence on policy rate. Specifically,

result revealed that while global oil price and inflation rate exert significant positive influence on policy rate with reported coefficient estimates of 1.073791 ($p < 0.05$) and 0.304021 ($p < 0.05$) respectively. Exchange rate and gross domestic product exert a significant negative impact on policy rate with a coefficient estimates of -0.275919 ($p < 0.05$) and 0.391941 ($p < 0.05$) respectively.

5.3 Cross-sectional analysis

Table 5 presents an overview of the short-run effect of determinant variables identified in this study on policy rates for the WAMZ countries. As reported, the result in the Federal funds rate and trade openness has a significant short-run influence on the policy rate for the Gambia with a record of 0.023% and 0.191%, respectively. This may not be unconnected with the structure of the economy of the country; the country is import-dependent with an insubstantial export base.

For Ghana, all the determinant variables identified in this study have a significant influence on the policy rate. Specifically, the results show statistical estimates of 0.013%, 0.111%, 0.11%, 0.011%, 0.935%, 0.711%, and 0.171% for Federal funds rates, global oil price, trade openness, exchange rate and inflation respectively.

In the case of Nigeria, all determinant variables except the federal fund rate exert a significant effect on the policy rate with the rate of 0.0002%, 0.022%, 0.003%, 0.160%, 0.264% and 0.057% for Federal funds rate, global oil price, trade openness exchange rate inflation and growth respectively.

Table 5: Cross-sectional Short run Estimation Result (WAMZ)

Variables	Gambia	Ghana	Nigeria	Sierra Leone
COINTEQ01	-0.170874*	-0.028428*	-0.154490*	-0.038543*
D(MPR(-1))	0.438455*	0.460461*	0.402253*	0.353236*
D(MPR(-2))	0.016394**	0.100694*	0.158402*	0.127582*
D(FFR)	-0.023217**	-0.012873*	0.000178	0.001388*
D(GPR)	0.023218	-0.110961*	-0.022197**	0.001068
D(TOP)	0.190704*	-0.010744*	-0.002638*	0.006922*
D(EXC)	-1.876670	-0.935724*	0.160190*	-0.218865*
D(INF)	6.531080	0.710756*	-0.264159*	0.527974*
D(GDP)	0.246643	-0.171284*	-0.057285*	-0.104955*
C	1.025725	0.238252*	1.567039	0.355563

Source: Author's computation from data obtained from WDI and AfDB (2021).

In Sierra Leone, all the determinant variables except global oil price exert significant influence on policy rate. Specifically, at the rate of 0.0013%, 0.007%, 0.219%, 0.528%, and 0.105% for the variables of Federal funds rate, trade openness, exchange rates, inflation, and growth respectively.

Generally, in WAMZ, in the long run, global oil price (GPR), exchange rate (EXC), inflation rate (INF) and gross domestic product (GDP) exert a significant positive influence on policy rate. Comparatively, this pattern of relationship is similar to [30], which emphasized direct relationship between policy rates and macroeconomic variables. However, this is contrary to the findings of [23]. In the short run the combined overview of short run effect for WAMZ countries revealed that the determinant variables insignificantly affect policy rate.

On the cross-sectional analysis, In WAMZ the summary of the result showed that determinant variables such as federal fund rate, global oil price, trade openness, exchange rate, inflation rate, and the gross domestic product have a significant short-run influence on the policy rate of most of the WAMZ countries except in the case on Gambia where only federal fund rate and trade openness exert a significant effect on policy rate. This implies that a rise in the prices of these variables has a strong impact on the variations in the policy rates in member countries of WAMZ.

Conclusion

In summary, the noteworthy results derived from this study reveal that in the long run, the drivers of the monetary policy rate in the member countries of WAMZ include global oil price, exchange rate, inflation rate, and gross domestic product. While in the short run for most of the WAMZ countries especially, the federal fund rate, trade openness, exchange rate, inflation rate and gross domestic product are core driving factors of the policy rate. Hence this study concludes that to ensure long-run stability in the policy rate among the members' states, the determinants should be given closer consideration by the monetary authorities in this zone for better policy framework with a view to enhancing growth and economic stability. An area of further study on this topic or related topics can be the impact of fiscal policy measures.

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